

Screening of elite rice strains and varieties for bacterial blight (BB) resistance

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, is a major rice disease in the Tarai region of western Uttar Pradesh, and incidence is increasing throughout the state. In 1983 kharif, 6 All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) variety trials—uniform varietal trials 1, 2, and 3; preliminary variety trials 2 and 3; and Aromatic Slender Grain Varietal Trial (ASGVT), with 15, 22, 30, 64, 64, and 22 entries, were evaluated for BB incidence in replicated trials at the Crop Research Center of G. B. Pant University. Environmental conditions favored natural disease development and BB incidence was very high. Disease reaction was recorded at 50% flowering stage on a 0-9 scale.

Of 317 entries evaluated, 37 showed resistant reaction (3) (see table). The resistant entries were evaluated under

Rice varieties with field resistance to BB at Pantnagar in 1983 kharif.

Experiment	Varieties or elite strains with BB resistance
UVT 1	RP1670-1418-2205-1582 (IET7613), Govind, Cauvery
UVT 2	CR200-788-3 (IET6775), CR167-7 (IET4507), AD9246 (IET6985), OR173-1-1 (IET7179), RP1036-35-2-5-1-1 (IET7230), PR103 (IET7267), Pusa 205-15-1 (IET7279), CR163-CRRD-50 (IET780), CR75-93 Mut. 11-4 (IET7713)
UVT 3	IR54 (IET7296), or 147-1-137 (IET7174), Pant Dhan 4
PVT 2	RP1575-636-6-1 (IET8713), RP1775-243-719-681 (IET8718), NDR302 (IET8054), KR10-47 (IET8055), RAU4056-53-5, (IET8056), or 79-21 (IET5975), SKL 6 (IET7169), or 131-5-8 (IET7433), HPU804 (IET7500), BPT1235 (IET8040), BIET263 RAU49 (IET8044), UPR79-164 (IET8048), UPR254-21-1-1 (IET8049), UPR103-44-2 (IET8050), NDR301 (IET8053), NSRP11 Late (IET8700), BAU4090-1 (IET8702), UPR81-44 (IET8709), BK670 (IET8711), NRL 326-3 (IET8713), Rasi, Prasad
PVT 3	Pant Dhan 4

artificial epiphytotic conditions in 1984 kharif using standard clipping for disease inoculation. Under heavy BB pressure, all entries had susceptible reaction, scoring between 7 and 9. Results show that presently available elite materials in AICRIP trials have a low level of BB resistance. Therefore, there is a need to increase the level of resistance by incorporating new resistance genes into elite lines to combine stability with higher yields. DV85 and BJ1, which showed resistance at Pantnagar under artificial epiphytotic conditions, might be used as donors. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to black bug *Scotinophara coarctata*

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The first reported black bug outbreak in the Philippines was in Bonobono, Bataraza, southern Palawan, in 1982. Rices were screened for black bug resistance in a farmer field at Maasin, Brookes Point, in Jul-Dec 1983.

Three hundred rice breeding lines were sown in thermo cups and transplanted in caged plots at 15 test entries/plot and 10 hills/entry, 2-3 seedlings/hill. Water was maintained 3-5 cm deep for 20 d after

transplanting (DT). Field-collected black bug adults were introduced 20 DT at 5 bugs/hill (750 black bugs/test cage plot). Plot size was 1.5 × 3 m. Immediately after infestation, the field was drained, which favored black bug survival. The field remained saturated throughout the experiment.

Of the 300 rices screened, 20 were selected based on damage reaction. They were retested in the same field in Jan-May 1984 with 35 black bug adults/hill and treatments in 4 replications. The number of black bugs in 5 randomly chosen hills/test entry was recorded 20 d after infestation (DAI). Plant damage was rated at 20, 40, and 60 DAI based on the following scale:

Rating	Description
0	No damage.
1	Wilting of youngest leaf.
3	Wilting of youngest leaf and partial yellowing of the first, second, and third older leaves.
5	Wilting of more than two leaves and pronounced yellowing of the first, second, and third older leaves.
7	More than half the plants wilting or dead and remaining plants severely stunted.
9	All plants dead or bugburned.